

Studies of solar effect of safranine, methylene blue and Azur-B with reductants and their photogalvanic effect

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Abstract : Photochemical studies of dyes has contributed to the understanding of the mechanism of electron transfer reactions in photoelectro-chemical devices¹⁻⁶. A number of photoinduced redox reactions have been studied. These reactions prove to be helpful in electrochemical cell for the conversion of solar energy to electrical energy by chemical means⁷⁻⁹. It has been found that phenazine dyes in conjunction with different reducing agents is efficient photosensitizers for probing charge transfer in photochemical cells¹⁻⁸. Studies carried out by Isabel *et al.*⁹ on the photo redox reactions of thionine with iron(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II) by flash photolysis techniques provided better understanding of the mechanism of thionine based photogalvanic cell. A detailed literature survey¹⁻²³ reveals that different photosensitizers mainly cationic and neutral dyes and reductants have been used in photogalvanic cells but the use of combination of anionic, cations and neutral dyes as photosensitizers in the photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion and storage is rare, and hence the present work is undertaken. The system consisting of anionic dye safranine in aqueous solution generates photovoltage when studied in photogalvanic cell. The open circuit photovoltage, the short circuit current and solar energy efficiency of these systems have been determined. The effect of different parameters on electrical output of the cell were observed and a mechanism has also been proposed for the generation of photocurrent in photogalvanic cell.

Keywords : Solar effect, Azur-B, safranine, methylene blue, photogalvanic effect.

Purpose of the work :

The high-energy consumption has traditionally been associated with high quality of life, which often associated with the gross national product. Energy is consumed for variety of our needs and has become an essential ingredient of everyday life. There is a very good co-relation between the quantum of energy used by any nation and its development. The major conventional energy sources like wood, coal, petrol and diesel etc. are exhausting in a very rapid rate. The era has been started to see energy crises all over the globe. The scientists have to be learned in finding out energy sources, which prove to be non-polluting, inexhaustible and can fulfil the energy demands of the world. Solar energy is not only a non-polluting, inexhaustible and harmless but clean, low cost and hazardless with no disposable problem.

Approach :

(a) *Research design :* The present work is studied by observing photopotential and photocurrent of mixture of dyes in photogalvanic cell, which contain photosensitizer, reductant and surfactant in alkaline medium on the basis of photopotential and photocurrent, further parameters suited like power point, current of short circuit, conversion

efficiency, fill factor, storage capacity etc. The effect of pH, electrode area, diffusion length (distance between two limbs of H-tube) concentration of photosensitizer, reductant and surfactant is also studied.

(b) *Methodology :* A H-shaped tube was used which was filled with known amount of solution of photosensitizers, sodium hydroxide, surfactants, reductants and distilled water so as to keep the total volume of mixture always 25 ml. A platinum electrode (1.0 × 1.0 cm²) was dipped in one limb of the cell and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was immersed in another limb of the tube. The terminals of the electrodes were connected to digital pH meter (Systronics model 353) and the whole cell was kept in dark. The potential (mV) was measured in dark when the cell attains stable potential. Then the limb containing platinum electrode exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (ECE). Light intensity was varied by employing lamps of different voltage. A water filter was placed between the illuminated chamber and light source to cut off infrared radiation.

Scientific innovation and relevance :

The nature has been utilizing only 0.025% of solar energy in form of photosynthesis and is sufficient to feed

the whole world. Hence one can easily appreciate the solar input on the earth, which is sufficient to accommodate all energy needs of the world. The photoelectro-chemical effect is basis for this purpose, which may be defined as change in electrode potential (in open circuit) or the current flowing (in closed circuit) in an electrode/electrolyte system on generating electroactivity species.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of [EDTA] concentration :

The electrical output of the cell was affected by the variation of reducing agent concentration (EDTA) in the system, the results are summarized in Table 1. Lower concentration of reducing agents resulted in a fall in electrical output because fewer reducing agent molecules were available for electron donation to dye molecules.

Table 1. Effect of variation of [EDTA] concentration

[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}				
[MB] = 4.64×10^{-5}	pH = 12.78				
	Temp = 303 K				
	[EDTA] $\times 10^3 M$				
	2.52	2.56	2.60	2.64	2.68
Photopotential (mV)	590.0	710.0	860.0	672.0	547.0
Photocurrent (μA)	95.0	175.0	255.0	125.0	55.0
Power (μW)	57.03	124.25	218.80	85.04	28.10

Large concentration of reducing agent again resulted into a decrease in electrical output, because the large number of reducing agent molecules hinder the dye molecules reaching the electrode in the desired time limit.

Effect of variation of pH :

The electrical output of the cell was affected by the variation in pH of the system. It is observed from Table 2 that there is an increase in electrical output of the cell with the increase in pH values. At pH 12.78 a maxima was obtained. On further increase in pH, there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent. Thus, photogalvanic cells containing the Safranine-Methylene Blue-EDTA-Azur-B system were found to be quite sensitive to the pH of the solutions.

It was observed that the pH for the optimum condition was a relation with pK_a of the reductant and the desired pH is higher than its pK_a value ($pH > pK_a$). The reason may be the availability of reductant in its anionic form, which is a better donor form.

Table 2. Effect of variation of pH

[Azur-B] = $4.96 \times 10^{-5} M$	[EDTA] = $2.60 \times 10^{-3} M$				
[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	Temp. = 303 K				
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}				
	pH				
	12.65	12.70	12.78	12.83	12.85
Photopotential (mV)	185.0	617.0	860.0	261.0	107.0
Photocurrent (μA)	45.0	125.0	255.0	85.0	45.0
Power (μW)	77.40	78.44	218.0	75.4	45.80

Effect of variation of [Azur-B] (dye) concentration :

Dependence of photopotential and photocurrent on the concentration of Azur-B (dye) was studied and the results are summarized in Table 3.

Lower concentration of dye resulted into a fall in photopotential and photocurrent because fewer dye molecules are available for the excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode. The greater concentration of dye again resulted into a decrease in electrical output as the intensity of light reaching the dye molecule near the electrode decreases due to absorption of the major portion of the light by dye molecules present in path.

Table 3. Effect of variation of [Azur-B (dye)] concentration

[EDTA] = $2.60 \times 10^{-3} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}				
[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	pH = 12.78				
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	Temp. = 303 K				
	[Azur-B] $\times 10^5 M$				
	4.40	4.48	4.64	4.80	4.96
Photopotential (mV)	309.0	547.0	860.0	525.0	235.0
Photocurrent (μA)	45.0	55.0	255.0	80.0	35.0
Power (μW)	17.16	27.10	218.75	42.62	74.00

Effect of variation of [Safranine] concentration :

It was observed that the photopotential and photocurrent were increased with the increase in concentration of the safranine. A maximum was obtained for a particular value of safranine concentration, above which a decrease in the electrical output of the cell was obtained. The effect of variation of safranine concentration of photopotential and photocurrent are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of variation of [Safranin] concentration

[EDTA] = $2.60 \times 10^{-3} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}				
[Azur-B] = $4.96 \times 10^{-5} M$	Temp. = 303 K				
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	[Safranin] $\times 10^{-6} M$				
	3.20	3.80	4.00	4.40	4.80
Photopotential (mV)	624.0	805.0	860.0	750.0	740.0
Photocurrent (μA)	175.0	205.0	255.0	215.0	170.0
Power (μW)	202.0	210.0	218.0	215.0	207.0

Effect of variation of methylene blue concentration :

Table 5. Effect of variation of [MB] concentration

[EDTA] = $2.60 \times 10^{-3} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}				
[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	Temp. = 303 K				
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	pH = 12.78				
	[MB] $\times 10^{-5} M$				
	4.12	4.32	4.64	4.78	4.96
Photopotential (mV)	790.0	810.0	860.0	790.0	770.0
Photocurrent (μA)	205.0	220.0	255.0	215.0	202.0
Power (μW)	204.0	213.0	218.0	212.0	200.0

Effect of diffusion length :

The effect of variation of diffusion length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameters of the cell was studied using H-cells of different dimension. The results are reported in Table 6.

It was observed that there was sharp increase in photocurrent i_{max} in the first few minutes of illumination and then there was a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. This photocurrent at equilibrium is represented as (i_{eq}). This kind of photocurrent behaviour is an initial rapid reaction followed by a slow rate determining step at a later stage.

On the basis of the effect of diffusion path length on the current parameters, as investigated by Keneko and Yamada⁶ it may be concluded that the leuco or semi reduced form of dye and the dye are the main electroactive species at the illuminated and the dark electrodes, respectively. However, the reducing agents and its oxidized products behave as the electron carries in the cell diffusing through the path.

Table 6. Effect of diffusion length

[Azur-B] = $4.96 \times 10^{-5} M$	[EDTA] = $2.60 \times 10^{-3} M$		
[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	pH = 12.78		
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	Temp. = 303 K		
	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}		
Diffusion path length D_L (mm)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current (μA) min^{-1}
35.0	225.0	154.0	14.26
40.0	232.0	164.0	15.34
45.0	238.0	167.0	16.34
50.0	245.0	171.0	17.64
55.0	255.0	175.0	18.20

Current-voltage (i-V) characteristics and conversion efficiency :

It was observed that i-V curve of the cell deviated from its regular rectangular shape as given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Current-voltage (i-V) curve of the cell.

A point on the i-V curve called the power point (PP) was determined where the product of potential and current was maximum. The value of potential and current at the power point are represented as V_{pp} and i_{pp} , respectively. With the help of i-V curve the fill factor and the conversion efficiency of cell were determined as 0.45 and 1.20%, respectively, using the following formulae.

$$\text{Fill factor} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}}$$

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}} \times 100\%$$

where V_{pp} , i_{pp} , V_{oc} and i_{sc} , are the potential at power point, current at power point, open circuit voltage and short circuit current, respectively. The system (at its optimum condition) was exposed to sunlight. The conversion data for the photogalvanic cell is reported in Table 7.

Table 7. Conversion efficiency and sunlight conversion data

[Azur-B] = $4.96 \times 10^{-5} M$	[EDTA] = $2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$		
[Saf] = $4.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	pH = 12.78, Temp. = 303 K		
[MB] = $4.64 \times 10^{-5} M$	Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2}		
	Conversion efficiency (%)	Sunlight conversion data	
		Photo-potential (mV)	Photo-current (μA)
Dye + EDTA	0.282	765.0	175.0
MCx@dye + EDTA	0.678	860.0	255.0

Electroactive species :

Various probable processes may be considered for the photocurrent generation in photogalvanic cell. The results of the effect of diffusion length on current parameters were utilized to know more about the electroactive species. The possible combinations of electroactive species in photogalvanic cell are tabulated in Table 8.

Table 8. Possible combination for electroactive species

In illuminated chamber	In dark chamber
Dyes	Oxidized form of reductant (R^+)
Luco or semi dyes	Oxidized form of reductant (R^+)
Leuco or semi dyes	Dyes

The oxidized form of the reductant is formed only in the illuminated chamber and if it is considered to be the electroactive species in the dark chamber then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to accept an electron from the electrode. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of increase in photocurrent should decrease with an increase in diffusion length, but this was not observed experimentally. The value (i_{eq}) was also observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length (rather it decreases slightly). Therefore, it may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi-dye and the dye Azur-B, safranine and methylene blue in illuminated chamber and dark chamber respectively. However, the reductant and its oxidized products act only as electron carrier in the path.

Mechanism :

The various steps that take place in the photoredox reaction leading to the generation of photovoltage in the cell consisting of dyes and studied ions (Q) in the anode compartment and I_2/I^- in the cathode compartment are :

At the anode chamber :

At cathode chamber :

Here D^+ and DH^+ represent dye and semi dye radical ions respectively, methylene blue dye in the excited state is reduced to semi-form by the ions, which is converted to Q by donating a long pair of electrons at the photo anode the reduced dye donates an electron which move through the outer circuit and reduces I_2 to I^- or other reduced forms.

When the anionic dyes Azur-B and methylene blue are used in photoanode the following reaction may take place :

D^{-2} is anion radical of dye.

Among the dyes the anionic dye produces large photovoltage. Thus the photogalvanic cell containing dye absorbs photon energy and this energy is converted into electrical energy by the electrode reaction through the formation of an excited state complex of electron donor acceptor (EDTA) type.

Conclusion :

Photogalvanic effect : The photogalvanic effect of Azur-B, methylene blue and safranine were studied in aqueous solution using platinum electrode in chamber and saturated calomel electrode in other at 25 °C. On illumination, the anode compartment of the cell consisting of aqueous solution of dye and the ions studied a photovoltage develops which attains a maximum value within 30 min.

Azur-B produces much greater photovoltage compared to other dyes. When illumination is stopped the photovoltage decreases gradually and after a while the dark value is reached. The reversible light induced photovoltage generation can be reproduced at least 7–8 times. The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) has been found to increase with

increasing concentration of dye to generate maximum open circuit photovoltage at a fixed concentration of ions is given in Table 2.

But V_{oc} has found to remain the same with increasing concentration of ions at a fixed concentration of dye ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$). The growth of photovoltage of the cell consisting of aqueous solution of dyes in the anode compartment and I_2/I^- redox couple in the cathode compartment are given in Table 5. From the current voltage curve of these systems, characteristics of photogalvanic cell i.e. short circuit current (I_{sc}) and solar energy efficiency (SEE) of these systems have been calculated using the following relations and given in Table 5.

$$\text{Fill factor (ff)} = (V_{pp} \times I_{pp}) / (V_{oc} \times I_{sc})$$

where V_{pp} and I_{pp} are the potential and current at power point, which is a point on the current-voltage curve where the product of current and potential was maximum.

$$\text{SEE} = \frac{\text{Power generated in cell/cm}^2}{\text{Power of incident photon/cm}^2}$$

$$\text{Power of cell} = \frac{I_{sc} V_{oc} \text{ ff}}{\text{Area of electrode}}$$

The results indicate that for different dyes the photovoltage generated follows the order : Azur-B > safranin > methylene blue. Among the different redox couples, which are easy to prepare the photovoltage generation becomes maximum with redox couple in cathode. Since EDTA is a universal donor and has been used in earlier work⁶ it has also been used with dye in photo anode compartment like other ions but the photovoltage generation is much less compared to anion. It is interesting to mention that photovoltage growth and decay of dye-ion system in aqueous solution follow the functional forms as follows :

$$V_e = V_o [1 - \exp(-t/t_1) + Z_2]$$

$$V_i = V_o [1 - \exp(-t/t_2) + Z_2]$$

where V_i is open circuit voltage at time t , V_o the study state maximum open circuit voltage, t_1 and t_2 are the relaxation times for growth and decay respectively and Z_1 and Z_2 are constants for the system.

Cell performance :

The performance of the cell was studied by applying the external load necessary to maintain current and potential at the power point after removing the source of light until the output (power) to its half value at the power point in the dark. It was observed that the cell can be used in the dark at its power point for 62.0 min.

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